

ROLE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN ORGANIZING INDEPENDENT EDUCATION IN HISTORY

Userbayeva Feruza Inoyat kiz

Student of Chirchik State Pedagogical University

(998-94) 611-16-05 feruzauserbayeva@gmail.com

Abstract: This article talks about the importance of organizing independent education in the teaching of History. Also, some of our comments on the achievements of the organization of independent education are included in this article. The role and importance of modern technologies in the implementation of independent education are discussed, and our opinions on the results and achievements of applying modern technologies to this process are presented.

Key words: Approach, analysis, technique, system, independent, actual, pedagogue, education, information.

TARIX FANIDA MUSTAQIL TA'LIMNI TASHKIL ETISHDA ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALARNING O'RNI

Userbayeva Feruza Inoyat qizi

Chirchiq davlat pedagogika unversiteti talabasi

feruzauserbayeva@gmail.com

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Tarix fanini o'qitishda mustaqil ta'limni tashkil etishning ahamiyati haqida so'z boradi. Hamda mustaqil ta'limning tashkil etishning yutuqlari borasida ayrim mulohazalarimiz ham ushbu maqolamizda o'rin olgandir. Mustaqil ta'limni joriy etishda zamonaviy texnologiyalarni o'rni va ahamiyati haqida ham fikr yuritilib, ushbu jorayonga zamonaviy texnologiyalarni qo'llashning natija va yutuqlari borasida fikrlarimiz bayon etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Yondashuv, tahlil, texnika, tizim, mustaqil, dolzarb, pedagog, ta'lim, axborot.

РОЛЬ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ САМОСТОЯТЕЛЬНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ ПО ИСТОРИИ

Усербаета Феруза Инайят кизи

Студентка Чирчикского государственного педагогического университета
feruzauserbayeva@gmail.com

Аннотация: В данной статье говорится о важности организации самостоятельного образования при преподавании истории. Также в данную статью включены некоторые наши комментарии о достижениях организации независимого образования. Обсуждаются роль и значение современных технологий в реализации самостоятельного образования, а также излагаются наши мнения о результатах и достижениях применения современных технологий в этом процессе.

Ключевые слова: Подход, анализ, методика, система, самостоятельный, актуальный, педагог, образование, информация.

Intoduction

The place and role of modern teaching methods, interactive methods, and innovative technologies in the training of qualified professionals in higher education institutions and faculties of our republic is extremely important. Knowledge, experience, and interactive methods of pedagogical technology and pedagogical skills ensure that students acquire knowledgeable, mature skills [1]. Today, the current problems of modern history lessons are to thoroughly analyze the main principles of modern development, carefully study all mass media and Internet information, take an integrated approach to them, correctly analyze the necessary information in the course of the lesson, and should convey to the minds of pupils and students. Necessary conditions and opportunities have been created for the young generation to become fully developed individuals who fully meet the requirements of the 21st century. Documents, programs and plans of state significance have been developed for specific, purposeful implementation of work in this regard. At the same time, a number of conceptual studies related to the qualities of students and their future teachers, their social, philosophical, psychological aspects, the legal basis of teaching history, and the methodological bases of factors affecting education and training in today's dangerous times. ideas are analyzed. The process of continuous education can solve complex problems only when it follows scientific-pedagogical principles [2]. In all forms and types of institutions of the continuous education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the educational process can be achieved by fully providing it from a scientific and methodological point of view. Changes that are constantly occurring in the field of the history education system from the outside are constantly putting the problems of science, technology, technology, production culture and daily pedagogical practice of students in front of the current education system. In this regard, in the system of history education, it is necessary to raise the efficiency of the research process of history to a higher level in terms of quality, to develop modern teaching and methodical complexes using advanced

pedagogical and information technologies, to form the content of education and to connect continuous education. state standards have been developed in accordance with them and are being implemented based on the characteristics of each subject. The reform of the structure and nature of education and personnel training in our country has also set clear tasks for the science of history. Such tasks include the entire set of problems related to the scientific provision of the purpose, essence, methods, tools and organizational forms of education and training, taking into account the prospects of success in the field of science, technology and technology, socio-economic development of the Republic [3]. Today, attention is paid to effective and systematic organization of the education system in our country. Of course, it is important to adapt the educational system to the requirements of the times, and to bring innovations to this system. Among these processes, the independent conduct of the educational system is also important.

Literature analysis and methodology

Effective organization of extracurricular activities has attracted the attention of teachers and designers in different periods. The first information about extracurricular activities can be found in Russian sources of the 18th century.

During this period, students in (noble boarding houses and general) schools read excerpts and essays from their translated works during their free time. The concept of “extracurricular work” appears for the first time in the works of V. Sheremetevsky in the 19th century. By the 60s and 70s of the 20th century, extracurricular activities were firmly established in the practice of Soviet schools, including Uzbekistan, and became an integral part of the pedagogical process. In current pedagogy, there are different definitions of the term “work outside the classroom”. I.A. Karimov defines it as follows: “Extracurricular activities are organized by the school in order to expand and deepen the knowledge skills of students, to develop individual abilities of students, as well as to organize their reasonable rest” [4].

At the same time, for a certain period of time, pedagogical technology has been considered as the implementation of the educational process with the help of technological tools. Only since the 70s, the essence of this concept begins to be interpreted in a new way in pedagogical literature. Japanese scientist T. Sakamoto recognizes that “teaching technology is a field of knowledge related to the system of guidelines that ensures the acceptability of teaching”.

In the educational system, the theory and practice of pedagogical technology have been studied independently for many years. As a result, one or another advanced methods aimed at improving the teaching process or developing the knowledge of students are gradually losing their position and moving away from the science of pedagogy. For

example, just think of the “Programmed Education” that caused a great stir in the 60s, or the former union-wide “Disruption Movement” in the 70s. Today, our country has enough opportunities to combine the scientific potential of specialists. Ensuring the unity of theory and practice paves the way for determining the true nature of pedagogical technology [5].

It is appropriate to pay special attention to educational activities in extracurricular activities. If we talk about the planning of educational work in extracurricular activities and the pedagogical requirements for it, the planning of the educational activities of students has its own rules. In this, the pedagogic class team gets to know the state of upbringing of each student, including the family life and conditions of students, parents’ sense of duty in raising children, and student’s attitude to daily changes, students’ national values and traditions. - the level of knowledge about customs, traditions, the work of scientists and thinkers who have grown up in their country, and it is necessary to study and diagnose others. The educational process and forms of educational work should be organized to meet the requirements of the current era [6].

Results and discussion

Since the ability of a person to independently evaluate is complex, one of the main directions in the work of history teachers should be the formation of independent thinking skills in students. Experience shows that by patiently and independently pursuing the work that has been started, they achieve their goals in life only when they reach the end. The organization of independent work plays a special role in the traditional education of students. Due to the extremely large flow of information and the development of science and technology, young students cannot convey their knowledge, no matter how skilled they are, no matter how much knowledge they have in the course of the lesson. The only way to fill it is the independent work of students.

Independent work of students in historical education is an integral element of the teaching process. It is impossible to ensure unity of teaching and independent studies of students without independent work. But can independent work be considered a teaching method? There were several points of view in this regard. Sometimes it was included in the formats of organizing educational work, types of teaching, and practical methods of teaching. In recent years, most methodological authors have included independent work in teaching methods, as it is one of the most common methods of solving educational issues, including independence of knowledge and reading. Even so, among teachers: if we have distinguished practical methods, methods of applying theoretical knowledge in practical work, why should we distinguish the method of independent work? After all, here too, the question that it is about exercises, solving problems, performing experiments is often raised again and again [7]. One of the most characteristic features of independent work

methods is that students perform without direct supervision. Independent work can be carried out by students in lessons by learning the text of new material, performing exercises, conducting experiments, observations, labor operations, and so on. A fairly common type of independent work is doing homework. The methods of independent work carry out educational, educational and developmental tasks, especially in the teaching of history. Independent work helps the development of thinking, skills and abilities, trains the individual's will [8]. Now let's consider the situations in which it is most appropriate to use independent work methods in history teaching:

Which tasks is this method particularly successful in solving?

It is especially effective to use this method in cases where the content of the educational material is?

In cases where the material is convenient for independent learning.

It is effective to use this method when students have what characteristics?

When students are ready to study this topic independently.

What opportunities should the student have to use this material?

All didactic and methodical materials are available for students to work independently, when they have enough time to organize it in class [9]. These are the most important aspects of independent work. Nowadays, a lot of attention is being paid to these aspects. Among these are the works on the organization of independent education. Nowadays, a lot of attention is being paid to these aspects.

Organization and implementation of independent education is carried out within the framework of science. Topics are given, and students conduct independent research on the topics. How this work is accepted is determined by the teacher. We will try to justify this through the table below;

The topic of independent work given in the history of Asian and African countries (new period).

№	Independent work topic	Acceptance	Forms for submission of independent work
1	China in the XIX-XX centuries economic situation	electron	1. Distribution 2. Video (based on the topic) 3. Electronic "quiz" test covering the topic 4. On the basis of the developed topic (project work, report, lesson development) 5. "Abstract" with a scientific basis

1. The development of independent education in history is based on modern approaches in the example of “Digital history”.¹

Conclusion

One of the main tasks of modern education in the current era of rapid integration of information is the development of a person who can independently analyze the events of the world. History, like other general educational subjects, has great opportunities to form students' independent thinking.

In a democratic society, individuals who can think freely have dignity. In turn, they can appreciate the aspirations and opinions of others. Dignity emerges as an important aspect of a person's social and spiritual freedom. Freedom is the first step towards independent thinking. The existence and development of independent thought largely depends on the level of freedom of students. It is necessary to achieve individual and collective freedom of students in order to form and develop independent thinking. Because independent thinking, as a personality trait, remains one of the important factors that ensure a high rate of individual and collective success in any type of activity. At the same time, independent thinking is a product of the opportunities and freedoms society has created for man. And thinking is a process of personal cognitive activity, characterized by a direct and generalized reflection of the event. One of the most characteristic features of independent work methods is that students perform educational tasks without the direct supervision of the teacher. Independent work can be carried out by students in lessons by studying the text of new material, performing exercises, conducting experiments, observations, labor operations, etc. A fairly common type of independent work is homework (oral, written, or experimental).

Independent work methods perform educational, educational and developmental tasks especially in history teaching. Independent work helps the development of thinking, skills and abilities, trains the individual's will [10]. Of course, we should emphasize that modern technologies are also very important in the implementation of these processes. Directing these technologies to the organization of an independent educational system in the educational system will give good and positive results. It also creates the ground for development in the modern age.

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